

ISic4383

Dedication to Orion, guardian of the Straits

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object

plaque

Editor

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Principal Contributor

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Autopsy

No autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Messana

Place of origin (modern)

Messina

Provenance

Found in secondary deposition in excavations of the mid-1990s in isola 84 at the corner of via E. Geraci and via C. Battisti, Messina

Coordinates

38.182439, 15.549211

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Messina, Soprintendenza stores, inventory ME 28244

Physical Description

A rectangular tablet of fine white marble, with a break down the middle and minor chipping to the edges. The rear is lightly convex, and smooth; the remains of a border along the upper rear face suggest the tablet has been re-used for the inscription.

Dimensions

Height 17-18 cm

Width 44 cm

Depth 3.5-4.5 cm

Layout

Five lines of Greek letters. The text observes a strict left margin, uneven at the right. The lines are regularly spaced and of equal height.

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Lunate Greek letters, neatly and regularly engraved, with only lightly pronounced terminal serifs. Alpha has an upward-sloping cross-bar. Beta is closed with almost equal eyes. Delta and Lambda extend the right hasta above the letter. Theta and Omicron are ovoid in form. Mu generally has vertical first and last strokes, with the middle-point only descending half-way.

Letter heights:

Line 1: 13 mm

Line 2: 10-12 mm

Line 3: 10-12 mm

Line 4: 10-13 mm

Line 5: 10-13 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation lines 1 to 5: 12-14 mm

Text

1. Χαῖρε μάκαρ χθονός ἡμετέρης βλάστημα σεβαστόν

2. Ζάγκλης εὐλιμένου μεδέων ἄκρης τε Πελώρου
3. εἰσορόων στεινόν τε πόρον καὶ ρεύματα πορθμοῦ
4. ἔνθα πάλιν φοῖτοιο διωκομένοιο κλυδῶνος
5. ἀντικορύσσεται Ἀδριακῶ Τυρρηνικόν ὕδωρ

Apparatus

Text after Ollà 2017 and photograph

Translation (en)

Hail, blessed one, august scion of our land, guardian of Zankle with its safe haven, and of Cape Peloros, watching over the narrow firth and the floodtide of the Straits, where, in the unceasing ebb and flow of the pursuing waves, the Tyrrhenian waters take up arms against the Adriatic.

Translation (it)

Salve, beato, germoglio venerabile della nostra terra, signore di Zancle dal bel porto e del capo Peloro, tu che guardi lo stretto passaggio e le correnti dello Stretto, dove, essendo l'onda sospinta avanti e indietro, il mar Tirreno si solleva contro l'Adriatico.

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

Bibliography

Ollà, A. 2017. Orione, "Signore di Zancle dal bel porto e del capo Peloro"? Prime osservazioni su un'epigrafe da via Geraci.. In Tigano, G.(eds.), *Da Zancle a Messina 2016. Nuovi dati di archeologia urbana*. Palermo. pp. 173-176.

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archivio fotografico della soprintendenza di Messina

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